

Photovoice

zine

Planning ENGLISH

Designing With Photovoice:
A Collaborative Curriculum of Becoming

USE your VOICE

IDENTITY
LITERACY

POETRY

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A Collaborative Curriculum of Becoming

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The Unit Plan:
Photovoice Poetry

Designing: Students, Centered

A Sonnet for the Students of Room 236

For all the bright young students rosters hold,
Designing is not bound by page or plan,
For by the roots of stories yet untold—
A welcome space for all—how we began.

The standards, cent'ring students, can be met,
So we, through art, designed plans for this goal:
Identity—CHRL begets,
A framework not to bind but make us whole.

The state expects a scope, a script, a score,
Instead, we built from questions about them.
Each photo its own text and something more—
A space to shape the self, a worthy gem.

Let poems then bloom from photos, grand and small—
Each design puts students above all.

Arts-Based Lesson Planning & Design

student-centered

We let color, visuals, and reflexive, arts-based practices guide our lesson design processes. This artistic focus allowed us to keep students at the center of all instructional decisions as it allowed us to slow down and be purposeful.

identity-focused

Figma - visual/digital lesson planning tool

Photography

WHAT THE PICTURE HOLDS

A Villanelle

Who am I?—the lens won't lie.
Images begin to speak, then hide.
I am what the picture holds.

A photograph—a pause, a watchful eye—
In policies and legislation, limitations reside.
Who am I?—the lens won't lie.

That which lies before me speaks of I,
To my sense of self I must abide.
I am what the picture holds.

To standards alone, should my teacher comply?
Or include students' stories, far and wide.
Who am I?—the lens won't lie.

No multiple choice could ever satisfy
what photos evoke and words confide.
I am what the picture holds.

This work—though some may wonder why—
is proof that photos, stories, and standards can coincide.

Who am I?—the lens won't lie.
I am what the picture holds.

Shakespeare Shapes the Space

A Sonnet to Shape the Self

We used *The Tempest*, both on page and screen—
A play to introduce Shakespearean style.
The text—on stage—a guide for things unseen;
To center students' selfhood all the while.

The style and rhythm of words a bit unique,
Yet tone and purpose—meaning—they reveal.
Meter, rhyme, and rhythm they did seek,
A frame of self through lens and poetry.

Through Shakespeare's guide, their images revealed—
Traditional yet fresh, each person known.
Their photographs and lines indeed appealed:
What counts as text, and who should set the tone?

To meet the standard is not to erase;
But to begin with voice—this we must face.

Who was William Shakespeare, and why do we care?

Introduction to *The Tempest* by William Shakespeare

Close to a Mediterranean island, a storm overcomes the ship that carries King Alonso of Naples, his son Ferdinand, his brother Sebastian, their friend Antonio the Duke of Milan, and various members of the court. On the shore of the island, Prospero, the former Duke of Milan, watches the storm with his fifteen year old daughter Miranda. As they watch events develop, Prospero tells Miranda their story. Prospero explains that twelve years ago his brother Antonio removed him from power. Antonio claimed Prospero's rightful dukedom for himself, forcing Prospero to leave. Prospero escaped in a boat with only the infant Miranda and his books of magic. They came to the island and made it their home and made the only native inhabitant -- Caliban -- their slave. Their only other companion is Ariel, a sprite that Prospero rescued and enslaved. Prospero reveals that he has arranged the storm and shipwreck, so he can get revenge on those who deprived him of his dukedom.

The court members come to shore all right but King Alonso is extremely upset, believing his son Ferdinand drowned when the ship was destroyed. In fact however Prince Ferdinand has landed elsewhere and is quite fine. Ferdinand meets Miranda and they fall immediately in love with each other.

Prospero decides to test the possible future husband of his daughter and captures Ferdinand, putting him to work carrying wood for his fire.

At Prospero's request, Ariel uses magic to lure the courtiers away while Antonio and Sebastian plan to kill King Alonso. Their plan is stopped however by Ariel who leads them all onwards seeking food and help. Meanwhile the court fool Trinculo has come to shore and discovered Caliban with whom he hides under a big coat until the storm has passed. The two are found by the ship's butler Stephano who, a bit tipsy, wonders if they are a two headed monster! Together they all get drunker and set off to find Prospero, deciding to kill him and make Stephano lord of the island. Ariel reports their plan to Prospero.

Prospero has decided that Ferdinand has passed his test and celebrates his engagement to Miranda by holding a masque (that is, a dance in which the guests are all traditionally masked) attended by spirits and goddesses. However halfway through he remembers Caliban's plot.

Finally Prospero asks Ariel to bring all the shipwrecked people together before him, but instead of acting out his revenge, he decides to forgive them -- claiming that he has been moved by Ariel's statement that even he, a spirit, feels for the humans. He accepts the return of his dukedom from Antonio, and Ferdinand and Miranda are formally betrothed. Ariel is set free and Caliban and the drunken sailors get a stern rebuke. The play ends with (almost) everyone celebrating their reunion.

The Messy Middle

A Villanelle

The schedule shifted despite our planned design.
She taught between the tests, emergencies, and change.
Still, students searched for self through photos defined.

Our co-designed unit—simultaneously aligned
While also facing adjustments, in need of rearrange.
The schedule shifted despite our planned design.

State test prep days added, a meeting reassigned,
Absences grew, sharing photos sometimes felt strange—
Still, students searched for self through photos defined.

Time was slipping away to meet the standards in mind,
So we provided AI scaffolds—our plan reframed.
The schedule shifted despite our planned design.

We stayed the course, supporting students in kind,
Made space for self despite all limits and change—
Still, students searched for self through photos defined.

This isn't neat. It requires commitment to find
Ways to center students despite all the strain.
The schedule shifted despite our planned design.
Still, students searched for self through photos defined.

Once we had to cancel a planning session due to when my family's stove broke and I had to be home during the scheduled planning time for the delivery of a new stove.

BARRIERS

limitations

A new Florida House Bill prevented the use of cell phones in classrooms, which added to the difficulty of students uploading photos into their shared Google folders to use for writing activities during class.

We pressed on despite teacher and student sickness, unexpected emergencies, potential of jury duty, additional state testing prep days, standardized testing interruptions to both planning and student learning.

4.1.24	Communication - Synchronous/ Real-Time (text)	J: Hey! Are we supposed to plan tomorrow? [redacted] and I have a massive agenda of things to plan together because I was out Friday and the end of the day Thursday sick that we are going to start tackling today, but I might need to make sure I have planning clear to work with her tomorrow. I forgot if we had plans to plan tomorrow but wanted to let you know
4.1.24	Communication - Synchronous/ Real-Time (text)	M: We were maybe because I was potentially going to be at jury duty, but I was excused. Yay. Either way I can't plan tomorrow because I have to help at this grad school symposium. I WILL because it does need to happen Sick again?? Nooo! Can we do Friday planning period for starters? Also, I'll get you the video lesson for Thursday/Friday ASAP!

disruptions!

This Room Holds More Than Work on Display

A Sonnet for Student' Space to Share

The classroom shifted, stories took the floor—
A gallery of selves, both dim and bright.
Two photographs, two poems, a vision more—
To speak and bring oneself into the light.

They stood—unsure at first, but courage grew—
The poem's lines gave life to each framed shot.
The villanelles and sonnets showed anew—
Each storied picture—banned—it was not.

The room was full—of teachers, peers, and guests,
Of eyes that came to see, and ears to hear.
And in that space, amid the quiet tests,
They spoke their truths: reflecting self so clear.

This wasn't just a showcase or display—
It was their world, storied their own way.

***NOTE: These participants' provided consent & assent forms to be identifiable in any photos associated with this study. See study's Appendix A.**

UNIT Plan

Photovoice POETRY

Lesson Goals

Students will be able to demonstrate their understanding of sonnets and villanelles.

Students will be able to explain how the structure of sonnets and villanelles influences the meaning of the poem.

Students will be able to apply their understanding of sonnets and villanelles by writing their own poems.

Students will be able to implement figurative language into their poems.

Students will be able to analyze the use of AI relative to the generation of poems relevant to their freewrites. (optional goal - modified lesson based on student needs)

Learner Outcomes

Formative Assessments

Freewrites
Photographs
Informal check-ins/conversations

Summative Assessment

Photovoice Poetry Presentations (ELA Expo) -- 2 poems and 2 photographs shared through a visual representation

Anchor Text

Multi-Layered Texts

7th Grade Florida B.E.S.T. ELA Standards

Standard

ELA.7.R.1.4

Analyze the impact of various poetic forms on meaning and style.

Clarification 1: Poetic forms used for this benchmark are sonnet and villanelle.

Clarification 2: Instruction in this benchmark should focus on how the structure of each poetic form affects its meaning.

The 5 Learning Pursuits

IDENTITY

Students will become more iterate in their own identities by taking photos of various things that represent who they are.

SKILLS

Students will demonstrate fluency in applying elements of figurative language, sonnets, and villanelles.

INTELLECT

Students will develop a contextual understanding of Shakespearean language. (Some students will increase their ability to use and assess AI as a generative tool.)

CRITICALITY

Students will challenge dominant pedagogy by critically applying their knowledge of villanelles and sonnets in innovative ways.

Joy

Students will share with their teacher and peers about who they are outside of school - this elicits joy!

ASSESSMENT (determine how each pursuit will be assessed)

Photovoice Poetry Presentations (ELA Expo)

Identity: Self-taken photographs

Skills: Poems (1 villanelle and 1 sonnet)

Intellect: Shakespearean elements of poetry (and for some students, the critical use of AI)

Criticality: Poems - (Who is writing the poem and why? What influence does the poetry structure have on the meaning of the poem?)

Joy: Photographs, freewriting, and poems

Unit 4:
Photovoice

Introduction to photovoice video

PHOTOVOICE POETRY

7th Grade English Language Arts

ESSENTIAL QUESTIONS

How can my photos tell stories about who I am?

What is the relationship between photovoice and poetry?

Why do my stories matter?

PHOTO FREWRITE – GOOGLE FORM

Choose 1 photo below and write for 3-minutes about what story or stories the photo tells.
Some questions to guide your thinking.

What do you see? Smell? Think? Hear? Wish for? Dream about? Feel?
What stories might these pictures tell?
What other images does it make me think about?

La Chua Trail - Paynes Prairie

Sunset at Crescent Beach

Gator Football game

Photo # *

- 1
 2
 3

Choose 1 photo below and write for 3-minutes about what story or stories the photo tells. *

Some questions to guide your thinking:

What do you see? Smell? Think? Hear? Wish for? Dream about? Feel?

What stories might these pictures tell?

What other images does it make me think about?

Your answer

Please answer the following question before submitting this form: Do you have at least 2 photos in your shared Google Folder? *

- Yes
 No

Submit

Clear form

WHAT'S NEXT?

WHERE ARE WE NOW? WHERE ARE WE HEADED?

1. We have started taking photos in our lifeworlds outside of school. What are **lifeworlds**? Lifeworlds are the areas of my life that I am a part of. This can include anything associated with my family, friends, hobbies, cultural affiliations, church or religious affiliations, neighborhood/community, school, and more.
2. What do my lifeworlds say about **who I am** and **what matters to me**?
3. How have my lifeworlds **shaped me** into **who I am** today and **who I am becoming**?
4. What am I **passionate** about?
5. How does or how could **poetry align with my passions**?

PROJECT TIMELINE

Take photos & upload to Google folder

Photo 1: Freewrite, Write a Sonnet

Photo 2: Freewrite, Write a Villanelle

Visually represent photos & poems

Complete Self-Assessment & Reflection

Present PHOTOVOICE POETRY at the

**7th Grade ELA
Photovoice Poetry Expo**

May 20
or
May 21

SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT DESCRIPTION & RUBRIC

7th Grade ELA:

Unit 4 Summative Assessment - Photovoice Poetry

For Unit 4 in 7th grade ELA, we have centered **PHOTOVOICE & POETRY** while reading/watching the *Temple*. Specifically, we have discussed poetic performance, sonnets, & villanelles. We have also reviewed several other literary elements in preparation for the FAST Reading. One of these elements, which will also be assessed in this summative, is figurative language (and how it can contribute to tone and meaning).

For this summative assessment, students will **create two poems** that complement two photographs: one being *temple...one sonnet & one villanelle*. While there will be some specific requirements, students will be able to choose how they want to visually represent their poems at the summative "7th Grade ELA PhotoVoice Poetry Expo" (5/20/21). No matter the choice, students will be expected to include the same criteria, as explained in the remaining description of this assignment and rubric.

Choices for the narrative format include:

- Vlog/Vlogging
- Zine
- Poster
- Social Media "Post"
- Diary Entry/Letter to Someone
- Poetry "Slide"
- Google Slides* (least time-consuming)
- How another idea? (check with [redacted])

Summative Assessment Rubric

Assessment Component	Meets Expectations (20 points)	Meets Expectations (15 points)	Approaching Expectations (10 points)	Beginning (5 points)	Not Meeting (0 points)
Photo 1	Students included a photograph that was relevant to their topic and clearly related to their poem.	Students included a photograph that was relevant to their topic.	Students included a photograph that was somewhat relevant to their topic.	Students included a photograph that was not clearly related to their topic.	Students did not include a photograph.
Sonnet	The student wrote a sonnet that followed the form of the sonnet structure.	The student wrote a sonnet that followed the form of the sonnet structure.	The student wrote a sonnet that followed the form of the sonnet structure.	The student wrote a sonnet that followed the form of the sonnet structure.	The student did not write a sonnet.
Photo 2	A photograph included that was relevant to their topic and clearly related to their poem.	A photograph included that was relevant to their topic.	A photograph included that was somewhat relevant to their topic.	A photograph included that was not clearly related to their topic.	Students did not include a photograph.
Villanelle	The student wrote a villanelle that followed the form of the villanelle structure.	The student wrote a villanelle that followed the form of the villanelle structure.	The student wrote a villanelle that followed the form of the villanelle structure.	The student wrote a villanelle that followed the form of the villanelle structure.	The student did not write a villanelle.
Figurative language	Students used figurative language in their poem to enhance meaning.	Students used figurative language in their poem.	Students used figurative language in their poem.	Students used figurative language in their poem.	Students did not use figurative language.
Quality of writing	Students wrote a poem that was clear, concise, and easy to read.	Students wrote a poem that was clear and easy to read.	Students wrote a poem that was somewhat clear and easy to read.	Students wrote a poem that was not clearly written.	Students did not write a poem.
Self-reflection	Students included a self-reflection that was relevant to their poem.	Students included a self-reflection that was relevant to their poem.	Students included a self-reflection that was somewhat relevant to their poem.	Students included a self-reflection that was not clearly related to their poem.	Students did not include a self-reflection.

FINAL PROJECT VISUAL REPRESENTATION CHOICES

★ Choices for the narrative format include:

- Lyric Rap/Song
- Zine
- Poster
- Social Media "Post"
- Diary Entry/Letter to Someone
- Poetry "Slam"
- Google Slides* (*least time-consuming*)
- *Have another idea?* (check with !)

POETRY REVIEW

Why Shakespeare Loved Iambic Pentameter

How to Write a Sonnet

Sonnet:

14 total lines, each line written in iambic pentameter (10 syllables of unstressed/stressed)
4 quatrains (4-line stanza)
1 couplet (2-line stanza)

How to Write a Villanelle

1. A
2. B
3. A
4. B
5. C
6. D
7. C
8. D
9. E
10. F
11. E
12. F
13. G
14. G

Villanelle:

1. A line 1
2. B
3. A line 2
4. A
5. B
6. A line 1
7. A
8. B
9. A line 2
10. A
11. B
12. A line 1
13. A
14. B
15. A line 2
16. A
17. B
18. A line 1
19. A line 2

PHOTOVOICE POETRY EXEMPLAR

(SONNET: MS. TAYLOR)

I have always had cats in my life. When I was born we had two cats named Bradley and Tigger, and when I was little (in my first year of being homeschooled, 1st grade) we lived for a year in a trailer by an orange grove in ██████████ where there was a colony of about 50 cats in our backyard. We named all of them. A lot of my play time as a child was spent with cats. Throughout my life, some of the cats we've had have been named: Sagwa, Wilbur, Sam, Indy, Bob, Agamemnon, Chess, Diana, Mrs. Diana, Mama Cat, Fluffy, Trippy, Disease-y (sad, yes), and many many more I can't think of now. I understand cats, and in tandem I feel that cats understand me, in the way that the rustling of wind through leaves understands me, the way the rhythm of ocean waves matches with my heartbeat, the way the rain fall knows my quietly hopeful soul.

Obtaining each of my girls, pictured above, happened by chance, and we are the perfect family of three now. Elyse, the stripey girl on the left, was found at my parents' house outside my childhood bedroom window in 2020. Miriam, in the tuxedo, was brought in as a stray cat to the UF Small Animal Hospital

██████████ They love each other so much, and we spend every moment together at home. My cats mean so much to me not only because I have had cats my whole life, but also because I love to care for other beings. I get most of my sense of happiness from giving to others, which is maybe (probably, definitely) why I became a teacher too. I live to love and be loved, and my squirrely girls give me just that every day.

1. A I've made my own small family with you two.
2. B I live to love you, live for you to thrive,
3. A I listen to your every meep and mew-
4. B I'll care for you as long as I'm alive.

5. C When life becomes a cold and hollow cave
6. D And anxious thoughts wear into me a hole
7. C Your purrs wrap 'round me like a rolling wave
8. D And bloom a garden in my lonely soul.

9. E I can't imagine what my days would be
10. F Without your soft fur curled up by my side.
11. E I'm grateful that you also care for me.]
12. F Without the words, just trust, our love's implied.

13. G And while someday we'll have to close a door,
14. G These words will hold my girls forevermore.

PHOTOVOICE POETRY EXEMPLAR

(SONNET: PROFESSOR COMMERET)

Around my neck, I wear a lanyard. It's like my own visual life mantra, symbolizing some of the things that give and bring meaning to my life. On it I have affixed several pins - some signify a moment in time or an experience I've had that I wish to hold dear. Some represent constructs to which I dedicate my life to: love, justice, perseverance, and peace. All symbolize joy. Though each pin stands for something personally meaningful to me, they also reflect the humanity I celebrate in others. By noticing my pins, others might see that I believe they have value and that their life is significant - that their worth is celebratory and should be treated as such. As a teacher, I am committed to lifelong learning and much of what I have learned and continue to learn is represented on this lanyard. Though tangible in nature, it represents the things in life that are far greater, all of which I seek to emulate each and every day.

1. A To see the things that matter much to me,
2. B Just look upon the pins around my neck.
3. A The stories that once were and yet to be,
4. B Of love surpassed a bushel and a peck.

5. C Adorned for all to see it simply means
6. D Committed to things greater than one's own.
7. C For life itself and all it daily brings
8. D Reminders that what's reaped may soon be sown.

9. E And like a tree that's dug by waters deep
10. F Our love for others blossoms as we learn
11. E Belonging everyone no more we weep
12. F Compassion freely giv'n and never earned.

13. G Joy and justice, peace for humankind
14. G Together we as one indeed will bind.

PHOTOVOICE POETRY EXEMPLAR

(VILLANELLE: MS. TAYLOR)

This is a photo I took of Gainesville, FL from the window of a (very tiny) airplane I was taking to Washington, D.C. to visit one of my best friends for Spring Break. I love how the lights of the city look almost like shiny little beads dotting an ornately patterned fabric. I have taken many similar photos of city lights and the sky out of the windows of airplanes throughout the last few years.

While I have made Gainesville my home over time, I know it will not be my home forever. I find myself on these planes because I am flying to other places where my heart is: with the people I love. My boyfriend lives in Seattle, WA, and my best friend lives in Washington, D.C. There was once a time when we all lived in the same city, we even all went to the same high school- but I wasn't as close with either of them then. It's crazy that now that I am the closest with each of them is when we are the furthest away.

Every long break from school I travel away from my home here to the homes where my heart lives. Over Winter Break I flew to Seattle, I visited Seattle and D.C. last summer, the spring break before that I was in Seattle, and the summer before that my best friend lived in New York City- and you guessed it, I was on a plane flying to see her there too.

Being in my once-early, now suddenly late- twenties has been an experience of trying to make home wherever I am, and not being totally sure of it. I feel at home here in Gainesville with a job I love, students and colleagues I love, friends I care for dearly- but I also know that I will have to move away from everything I've built here someday soon to build the life I've always wanted, someday with a husband and kids and a house and everything else I dream of in the isolation from my most loved ones now.

I feel like I am always getting on planes away from home to go home. And I can't wait until the days I don't have to travel to home, when home can always be with me.

Villanelle:

1. **A** line 1 I love to leave this homey place, it seems.
2. **B** The home is where the heart is, people say.
3. **A** line 2 I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.
4. **A** I've planned it out with complicated schemes.
5. **B** And every plane I board feels like headway.
6. **A** line 1 I love to leave this homey place, it seems.
7. **A** A future near my loved ones glints and gleams.
8. **B** A life where no one lives that far away.
9. **A** line 2 I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.
10. **A** I soar through inky skies of moon and beams.
11. **B** And watch my city glitter as it fades.
12. **A** I love to leave this homey place, it seems.
13. **A** A sadness in me sometimes softly screams
14. **B** Home now is just where my cats and I stay.
15. **A** line 2 I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.
16. **A** Someday I'll fly through final cool jet streams,
17. **B** For now I'll travel every Winter Break.
18. **A** I love to leave this homey place, it seems.
19. **A** I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.

PHOTOVOICE POETRY EXEMPLAR

(VILLANELLE: PROFESSOR COMMERET)

I moved with my husband and three daughters from Michigan to Florida three years ago. It was the furthest any of us have ever lived from our other relatives. Although it was hard to leave family and friends so many miles away, there are many things that keep us connected and looking forward to each "next time" we see each other. One of those things is an old garden gnome that we left behind in Michigan with my mom and dad. I am not quite sure how it started, but we began hiding the gnome at one another's house each time we have been together since the beginning of our time in Florida. It has not only become our little joke with one another, but - more importantly, it has become something we hold onto as a way of looking forward to the next time we are together. You never know where the little gnome is going to show up. I just found it again just the other day and it made me laugh out loud heartily, think of my loved ones back in Michigan, and long for the next time we get to be together. But for now, the gnome has its place in my home.

1. **A** It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
2. **B** Bright things ahead, new experiences yet to create
3. **A** Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.
4. **A** What once was still is, hope's alive in the garden gnome
5. **B** Though far away in a distant far off state,
6. **A** It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
7. **A** The quirky little figure keeps time like a metronome.
8. **B** To and fro it reminds us that our love is great!
9. **A** Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.
10. **A** It brings laughter and tears to discover his little dome
11. **B** To think fondly of each other, it elevates the heart rate
12. **A** It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
13. **A** Sometimes in a corner, in a box or under foam,
14. **B** To unearth the little guy is surely to elate
15. **A** Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.
16. **A** Our faraway love shines bright like polished chrome
17. **B** Though miles apart, each moment is one to celebrate
18. **A** It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
19. **A** Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.

GUIDED VISUAL BRAINSTORMING

1. In the center of your paper, write your first and last name.
2. Somewhere else on your page, draw a simple picture that represents one of your photographs you plan to write about (for example: I could draw a picture of a heart). Underneath the picture, write what the photo is (for example: lanyard with pins)
3. Draw an arrow from your name to the first picture.
4. Coming out from the picture you drew, write words or short phrases or draw simple pictures of things that come to mind about your photo, creating a web.
5. Repeat the steps for the second photo you plan to write about. This exercise will get you brainstorming before you freewrite for five minutes about each photo.
6. Turn in your visual brainstorming to Ms. [redacted]. She will hold onto these for next time.

EXAMPLE

Mind Maps

My MIND MAP exemplar

Mind maps provided another great scaffold for students to think about who they are outside of school. What lifeworlds are they a part of? What are they passionate about? What might they take photos of to represent these various characteristics?

PoetAI.io

Find rhymes, synonyms, adjectives, and more!

1. Model how to use AI Poet.io tool here using any of the previous four prompts (perhaps one sonnet & one villanelle). Simply COPY & PASTE the FREEWRITE.
2. Make revisions to the poem(s) based on word choice and accuracy to how well the AI-generation reflects one's story/sense of self.
3. Ensure that each poem includes one example of figurative language.

What is... **FIGURATIVE LANGUAGE?**

When words mean something other than their LITERAL meaning.

SIMILE	A comparison of two unlike things using "like" or "as".	My brothers are as loud as symbols clanging together.
METAPHOR	A comparison of two unlike things that says one thing "is" another.	The new baby was a bundle of joy.
HYPERBOLE	An EXAGGERATION that can't possibly be true.	It felt as if I had walked a million miles to school.
PERSONIFICATION	Giving human qualities to nonhuman things.	The morning sun smiled down on me as I walked to the bus.
ALLITERATION	The repetition of the same initial consonant sound.	He helped her hurt head heal.
ONOMATOPEIA	Words whose sounds suggest their meaning.	A snowball WHOOOSHED past my car during the snowball fight.
IDIOM	A group of words whose meaning isn't understood from their literal meanings.	After we won the soccer game, my team was on cloud 9.
ALLUSION	A reference to a famous person, place, or event.	The gold medal winner was a Cinderella story.
OXYMORON	A phrase whose words contradict each other with opposite meanings.	The adobe ranch was really pretty ugly.

WRITING TOOLS

[Rhyme Zone](#)

Find rhymes, synonyms, adjectives, and more!

WRITING TOOLS

[PoetAI.io](#)

PoetAI.io

AI Poem Generator

Introducing the revolutionary AI Poem Generator, an innovative tool that combines technology and creativity to turn a few simple words into stunning poetic masterpieces!

by DeepAI

[ChatGPT](#)

Important Note: At the time of this publication, this tool is no longer active. However, this is one of the websites utilized at the time of this study, along with Chat GPT. Another tool to consider may be AI Poem Generator. However, we do not have experience working with this tool.

photo VOICE

Poetry

Freewrite

This is a photo I took of Gainesville, FL from the window of a (very tiny) airplane I was taking to Washington, D.C. to visit one of my best friends for Spring Break. I love how the lights of the city look almost like shiny little beads dotting an ornately patterned fabric. I have taken many similar photos of city lights and the sky out of the windows of airplanes throughout the last few years.

While I have made Gainesville my home over time, I know it will not be my home forever. I find myself on these planes because I am flying to other places where my heart is: with the people I love. My boyfriend lives in Seattle, WA, and my best friend lives in Washington, D.C. There was once a time when we all lived in the same city, we even all went to the same high school- but I wasn't as close with either of them then. It's crazy that now that I am the closest with each of them is when we are the furthest away.

Every long break from school I travel away from my home here to the homes where my heart lives. Over Winter Break I flew to Seattle, I visited Seattle and D.C. last summer, the spring break before that I was in Seattle, and the summer before that my best friend lived in New York City- and you guessed it, I was on a plane flying to see her there too.

Being in my once-early, now suddenly late- twenties has been an experience of trying to make home wherever I am, and not being totally sure of it. I feel at home here in Gainesville with a job I love, students and colleagues I love, friends I care for dearly- but I also know that I will have to move away from everything I've built here someday soon to build the life I've always wanted, someday with a husband and kids and a house and everything else I dream of in the isolation from my most loved ones now.

I feel like I am always getting on planes away from home to go home. And I can't wait until the days I don't have to travel to home, when home can always be with me.

MS. TAYLOR'S VILLANELLE

1. **A** line 1 I love to leave this homey place, it seems.
2. **B** The home is where the heart is, people say.
3. **A** line 2 I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.

4. **A** I've planned it out with complicated schemes,
5. **B** And every plane I board feels like headway.
6. **A** line 1 I love to leave this homey place, it seems.

7. **A** A future near my loved ones glints and gleams,
8. **B** A life where no one lives that far away.
9. **A** line 2 I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.

10. **A** I soar through inky skies of moon and beams,
11. **B** And watch my city glitter as it fades.
12. **A** I love to leave this homey place, it seems.

13. **A** A sadness in me sometimes softly screams
14. **B** Home now is just where my cats and I stay-
15. **A** line 2 I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.

16. **A** Someday I'll fly through final cool jet streams,
17. **B** For now I'll travel every Winter Break.
18. **A** I love to leave this homey place, it seems.
19. **A** I wonder when my home won't live in dreams.

What do you want your poem to be about? *

- Provide a detailed description of your event, subject, or story to maximize personalization
- Make your poem truly unique by including specific details, names, and notes

My poem should be about how I often find myself on planes flying to see the people I am closest to emotionally, who are also those who live the furthest away physically. I am using a photo of the city where I live now from the window of an airplane, and the poem should reflect on how it seems like I love to leave the home where I live now, but I'm really just traveling to the homes where my heart is with the people I love.

Next →

In skies of blue, I find my heart astray,
A bird that flies to lands unknown, yet dear,
To souls that home my heart a world away.

Through clouds that part like curtains in their play,
I gaze upon the world so distant, near,
In skies of blue I find my heart astray.

Below, the city where I live, colors gray,
But love resides where family's laughter cheers,
To souls that home my heart a world away.

The whirring engines hum a lull, convey
My spirit to the ones who ease my fears,
In skies of blue I find my heart astray.

The plane, a vessel longing to convey
My presence to my loves, precious and clear,
To souls that home my heart a world away.

The city shrinks, a memory in the bay,
For home's not where I stay, but where love steers,
In skies of blue I find my heart astray,
To souls that home my heart a world away.

photo VOICE Poetry

Freewrite

Freewrite: I moved with my husband and three daughters from Michigan to Florida three years ago. It was the furthest any of us have ever lived from our other relatives. Although it was hard to leave family and friends so many miles away, there are many things that keep us connected and looking forward to each "next time" we see each other. One of those things is an old garden gnome that we left behind in Michigan with my mom and dad. I am not quite sure how it started, but we began hiding the gnome at one another's house each time we have been together since the beginning of our time in Florida. It has not only become our little joke with one another, but - more importantly, it has become something we hold onto as a way of looking forward to the next time we are together. You never know where the little gnome is going to show up. I just found it again just the other day and it made me laugh out loud heartily, think of my loved ones back in Michigan, and long for the next time we get to be together. But for now, the gnome has its place in my home.

MICHELLE'S VILLANELLE

1. A It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
2. B Bright things ahead, new experiences yet to create
3. A Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.
4. A What once was still is, hope's alive in the garden gnome
5. B Though far away in a distant far off state,
6. A It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
7. A The quirky little figure keeps time like a metronome.
8. B To and fro it reminds us that our love is great.
9. A Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.
10. A It brings laughter and tears to discover his little dome
11. B To think fondly of each other, it elevates the heart rate
12. A It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
13. A Sometimes in a corner, in a box or under foam,
14. B To unearth the little guy is surely to elate
15. A Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.
16. A Our faraway love shines bright like polished chrome
17. B Though miles apart, each moment is one to celebrate
18. A It may not seem like much, but it reminds me of home.
19. A Yet it is freeing to spread my wings, away I roam.

AI-Generated Villanelle:

In Michigan our gnome did stay,
A link to treasures held afar,
In Florida, we've found our way.

From family, we had to stray,
To new horizons, near and far,
In Michigan our gnome did stay.

With heartache, we faced the day,
Leaving loved ones like a scar,
In Florida, we've found our way.

But in this game we choose to play,
The gnome, a bond unlike a bar,
In Michigan our gnome did stay.

Each visit, hidden gnome's display,
A symbol of who we are,
In Florida, we've found our way.

Though miles apart, our hearts convey,
Our love remains a guiding star,
In Michigan our gnome did stay,
In Florida, we've found our way.

photo VOICE

Poetry

Freewrite

Freewrite:

I have always had cats in my life. When I was born we had two cats named Bradley and Tigger, and when I was little (in my first year of being homeschooled, 1st grade) we lived for a year in a trailer by an orange grove in [redacted] where there was a colony of about 50 cats in our backyard. We named all of them. A lot of my play time as a child was spent with cats. Throughout my life, some of the cats we've had have been named: Sagwa, Wilbur, Sam, Indy, Bob, Agamemnon, Chess, Diana, Mrs. Diana, Mama Cat, Fluffy, Trippy, Disease-y (sad, yes), and many many more I can't think of now. I understand cats, and in tandem I feel that cats understand me, in the way that the rustling of wind through leaves understands me, the way the rhythm of ocean waves matches with my heartbeat, the way rainfall knows my quietly hopeful soul.

Obtaining each of my girls, pictured above, happened by chance, and we are the perfect family of three now. Elyse, the stripey girl on the left, was found at my parents' house outside my childhood bedroom window in 2020. Miriam, in the tuxedo, was brought in as a stray cat to the [redacted]

and spend every moment together at home. My cats mean so much to me not only because I have had cats my whole life, but also because I love to care for other beings. I get most of my sense of happiness from giving to others, which is maybe (probably, definitely) why I became a teacher too. I live to love and be loved, and my squirrely girls give me just that every day.

MS. TAYLOR'S SONNET

1. **A** I've made my own small family with you two.
2. **B** I live to love you, live for you to thrive,
3. **A** I listen to your every meep and mew-
4. **B** I'll care for you as long as I'm alive.

5. **C** When life becomes a cold and hollow cave
6. **D** And anxious thoughts wear into me a hole
7. **C** Your purrs wrap 'round me like a rolling wave
8. **D** And bloom a garden in my lonely soul.

9. **E** I can't imagine what my days would be
10. **F** Without your soft fur curled up by my side.
11. **E** I'm grateful that you also care for me,
12. **F** Without the words, just trust, our love's implied.

13. **G** And while someday we'll have to close a door,
14. **G** These words will hold my girls forevermore.

AI-Generated Sonnet:

What do you want your poem to be about? -

- Provide a detailed description of your event, subject, or story to maximize personalization.
- Make your poem truly unique by including specific details, names, and notes

I want my poem to be about my two cats, Miriam and Elyse, and how they keep me from being lonely, anxious, and sad. They are like my family, and they help me feel like I can love and be loved. Even though pets' lives are short, I will love them long after they are gone because they are my first small family I have made on my own.

Next →

In hushed embrace, my feline family,
 Miriam and Elyse, bring solace near,
 Through fur and purrs, they mend my soul's decree,
 In their soft gaze, I find a love sincere.

In moments dark, when shadows start to creep,
 They weave a light through darkness deep and wide,
 With playful bounds, they chase away the sleep,
 Their gentle presence, always by my side.

Not mere companions, but kin close and dear,
 With every whisker, warmth and comfort blend,
 Their loyalty, a balm for every fear,
 A bond unbroken, held until the end.

Though fleeting be the lives they bravely roam,
 In me, their memory shall ever find a home.

photo VOICE Poetry

freewrite

Freewrite: Around my neck, I wear a lanyard. It's like my own visual life mantra, symbolizing some of the things that give and bring meaning to my life. On it I have affixed several pins - some signify a moment in time or an experience I've had that I wish to hold dear. Some represent constructs to which I dedicate my life to: love, justice, perseverance, and peace. All symbolize joy. Though each pin stands for something personally meaningful to me, they also reflect the humanity I celebrate in others. By noticing my pins, others might see that I believe they have value and that their life is significant - that their worth is celebratory and should be treated as such. As a teacher, I am committed to lifelong learning and much of what I have learned and continue to learn is represented on this lanyard. Though tangible in nature, it represents the things in life that are far greater, all of which I seek to emulate each and every day.

MICHELLE'S SONNET

1. A To see the things that matter much to me,
2. B Just look upon the pins around my neck.
3. A The stories that once were and yet to be,
4. B Of love surpassed a bushel and a peck.
5. C Adorned for all to see it simply means
6. D Committed to things greater than one's own.
7. C For life itself and all it daily brings
8. D Reminders that what's reaped may soon be sown.
9. E And like a tree that's dug by waters deep
10. F Our love for others blossoms as we learn
11. E Belonging everyone no more we weep
12. F Compassion freely giv'n and never earned.
13. G Joy and justice, peace for humankind
14. G Together we as one indeed will bind.

AI-Generated Sonnet:

Around my neck, a lanyard gently sways,
 A symbol of what brings my life its thrall,
 Each pin affixed, in vibrant colors blaze,
 A tale of moments, big and small in all.

Some pins for love, enduring and profound,
 A beacon in a world that craves for peace,
 For justice too, where truth and fairness abound,
 With perseverance, trials and strife will cease.

These symbols that I wear, they do extend,
 Beyond my own existence, they declare,
 A celebration of all, without end,
 Reflecting kindness and the joys we share.

For as a teacher, I aim to inspire,
 With every lesson learned, I never tire.

7th Grade ELA:

Unit 4 Summative Assessment - Photovoice Poetry

Assignment Description

☀️ For Unit 4 in 7th grade ELA, we have centered **PHOTOVOICE & POETRY** while reading/watching *The Tempest*. Specifically, we have discussed **iambic pentameter, sonnets, & villanelles**. We have also reviewed several other literary elements in preparation for the FAST - Reading. One of these elements, which will also be assessed in this summative, is **figurative language** (and how it can contribute to tone and meaning).

☀️ For this summative assessment, **students will craft two poems that complement two photographs they have taken - one sonnet & one villanelle. While there will be some specific requirements, students will be able to choose how they want to visually represent their poems at the culminating “ELA Photovoice Poetry Expo” on May 20 or 21.** No matter the choice, students will be expected to include the same criteria, as explained in the remaining description of this assignment and rubric.

☀️ Choices for the narrative format include:

- Lyric Rap/Song
- Zine
- Poster
- Social Media “Post”
- Diary Entry/Letter to Someone
- Poetry “Slam”
- Google Slides* (*least time-consuming*)
- *Have another idea?* (check with ██████████!)

Summative Assessment Rubric

Assessment Component	Mastery (4 points)	Meeting/ Proficient (3.39 points)	Approaching (2.79 points)	Beginning (2.19 points)	Not Meeting (1.5 points)
Photo # 1	A photo is included that was taken by the student. The photo represents something from one of the student's lifeworlds.	x	x	x	No photo is included.
Sonnet	The sonnet follows all syllable and rhyme scheme rules.	There is one mistake in relation to the sonnet's syllables or rhyme scheme.	There are two mistakes in relation to the sonnet's syllables or rhyme scheme.	There are three mistakes in relation to the sonnet's syllables or rhyme scheme.	There are four or more mistakes in relation to the sonnet's syllables or rhyme scheme.
Photo # 2	A photo is included that was taken by the student. The photo represents something from one of the student's lifeworlds.	x	x	x	No photo is included.
Villanelle	The villanelle follows all rhyme and line repetition rules.	There is one mistake in relation to the villanelle's rhyme and line repetition rules.	There are two mistakes in relation to the villanelle's rhyme and line repetition rules.	There are three mistakes in relation to the villanelle's rhyme and line repetition rules.	There are four or more mistakes in relation to the villanelle's rhyme and line repetition rules.
Figurative Language	<u>Each poem</u> has at least one effective use of figurative language to influence the poem's tone/meaning.	<u>One poem</u> has one effective use of figurative language to influence the poem's tone/meaning.	x	x	There are no evident instances of figurative language in either poem.
Accuracy (grammar, punctuation, capitalization, spelling)	There are 0-4 errors in grammar, punctuation, capitalization, and/or spelling.	There are 5-9 errors in grammar, punctuation, capitalization, and/or spelling.	There are 10-14 errors in grammar, punctuation, capitalization, and/or spelling.	There are 15-19 errors in grammar, punctuation, capitalization, and/or spelling.	There are 20+ errors in grammar, punctuation, capitalization, and/or spelling.
Habits of Work	Used all of class time wisely. Worked independently, asked questions when necessary, and demonstrated evidence of their best work.	Used most of class time wisely. Worked independently some of the time, asked questions only when prompted by others, and demonstrated evidence of quality work.	Used some of class time wisely. Worked independently occasionally, did not ask questions when stuck, and demonstrated minimal effort throughout work time to complete this assessment.	Used very little class time wisely. Did not work well independently, did not ask questions to assist in their work, and demonstrated very little effort on this assessment.	No class time was used wisely for this project. Did not work well independently and demonstrated little to no effort to complete this assessment.

Some notes on the use of AI...

I am thinking that everyone can play around with the AI tool, and we will ensure that students revise the poems as necessary to make sure that they accurately reflect what they want the poems to say. Additionally, providing a self-assessment and reflection at the end of this project will require students to describe how their AI-generated poems' structures effectively impact the tone/meaning of the poem. For students who are skilled writers, I would encourage them to write their own poems (or maybe write their own + an AI-generated one for each photo) and/or do more than two poems (other styles beyond sonnet/villanelle, if time permits). Due to time and to allow for critical analysis of the AI-tool, I think this could be a really neat learning experience for all/most. What do you think?
(5.8.24: Email, Michelle to Ms. Taylor)

Friday's observation went well. On Friday, Ms. Taylor connected the photographs that students have been taking and uploading for their final project with the poetry that they've been learning about, specifically sonnets and villanelles and iambic pentameter, in relation to a lot of which they've experienced through the watching of the Tempest the past several class periods, aside from testing. So, it was cool to see the connection and how they relate and what that looks like moving forward by introducing the summative assessment. So, the summative assessment is going to be where students write a sonnet and Villanelle after they free-write and think about why their photos -- the two photos, had significance to them in their lives. And they can either self-author the poems, one a sonnet, one a villanelle, or they can use AI-generated tool to assist them in the structure of that. And the purpose of that is not to take the easy way out or to cheat the system by any means, but rather to be more critical in terms of analyzing structure, accuracy, and relevance to them in their own lives. There wasn't enough time in Friday's lesson to show how that tool is used, but Ms. Taylor did at least reference it.
(5.14 - Michelle's analytic voice memo)

...they had an opportunity to free write and upload that free write into their AI generation tool to have the tool then generate a poem that reflected what they wanted it to say. Then many today talked about just how they went in and they said, Well, some of the things sounded like how I wanted it to sound, and other things weren't really... It didn't sound like my voice. They didn't sound like the kinds of words I would use, so I changed certain things around. Or others, like one student today, she talked about how she would not have really realized how she felt about the person she took a photo of if she had not used the AI-generated poem, because after her free write experience in putting that there.
(5.21 - Michelle's analytic voice memo)

